

Multiscale workflow for the profiling and identification of urinary food bioactives metabolites Part I: Optimizing urine extraction

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Urine is a valuable biofluid for monitoring human dietary exposure through omics techniques.
- Urine metabolites of food bioactives (FB) are highly heterogeneous and structurally variable.
- Accurate identification of urine FB metabolites is critical for exploration of their biological role.
- Comparison of different urine pretreatment protocols.
- Introduction of a simple urine pretreatment method with focus on large-scale potentials.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Food bioactives
Urine
Metabolism
Metabolic profiling
Sample preparation
High-scale extraction
Metabolite identification

ABSTRACT

Background: The relationship between diet, human health, and disease prevention is well-established, with food bioactive compounds (FBs) widely recognized for their beneficial effects. Metabolism is key in transforming precursor FBs molecules and facilitating their circulation in the human body. Urine has proven to be a valuable biofluid for monitoring dietary exposure. However, the low concentrations of FBs metabolites, their chemical variability, and the lack of appropriate reference standards present challenges in metabolite identification. To address these challenges, developing urine preparation methods for scalable metabolite isolation and unambiguous structure elucidation could significantly improve the coverage and accurate annotation of urine metabolites.

Results: Urine samples were collected from a healthy volunteer after hydroxytyrosol (HT) supplementation. Traditional urine pretreatment protocols, such as liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) and solid-phase extraction (SPE), were tested alongside enrichment methods using resins (XAD-4, XAD-7, ion-exchange). Extracts were analyzed in parallel using HPLC-DAD/ELSD, UPLC-HRMS, and NMR to assess profiles and annotate metabolites. Methods

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2025.343947>

Received 20 January 2025; Received in revised form 5 March 2025; Accepted 15 March 2025

Available online 22 March 2025

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were evaluated based on extraction yield, metabolite chemical and biochemical diversity, metabolite coverage, selectivity, as well as cost, ease and time. The most promising protocols were further tested on a larger scale. Among the methods evaluated, XAD-7 resin and LLE (Urine/EtOAc 1:3) showed the best performance. Furthermore, detailed identification of metabolites (endogenous and exogenous) per protocol was performed using LC-HRMS/MS and NMR. Additionally, investigation of each protocol performance in respect to the biochemical pathway in which metabolites are implicated was assessed.

Significance: The suggested workflow is compatible with both profiling and isolation set-ups and could provide essential insights into urine metabolome and FBs biotransformation. It ensures confident identification and high coverage of metabolites, providing more complete and accurate interpretation of metabolism studies' results and, therefore, valuable input in profiling approaches towards the role of diet on human health.

1. Introduction

Personalized nutrition, combined with the consumption of foods rich in biologically active compounds, or food bioactives (FBs), has emerged in recent years as a dynamic dietary approach aiming for disease prevention and enhancement of human health and well-being [1]. FBs function as extra nutrients, offering health benefits that extend beyond basic nutritional value. In the human body, FBs typically exhibit low oral bioavailability and undergo extensive metabolism and structural transformations. These processes are driven by phase I reactions (e.g., oxidation, reduction, hydrolysis), phase II reactions (e.g., glucuronidation, methylation, sulfation), and by gut microbiota-mediated metabolism (e.g., ring fission, hydrolysis, demethylation, reduction, decarboxylation, dehydroxylation, isomerization) [2,3]. Understanding the mechanisms of action of FBs and their role in promoting health, requires detailed elucidation of their metabolic pathways, beginning with the precise identification of their metabolites.

Liquid chromatography - mass spectrometry (LC-MS) platforms are predominantly employed to investigate the biotransformation of FBs and to annotate their metabolism products. At the heart of these studies lie -omics strategies, particularly metabolomics, which leverage advanced analytical methods and technologies [4,5]. The primary aim is to assess metabolome responses to specific dietary interventions and FBs consumption, while also identifying and monitoring FB-related biomarkers within a holistic framework [4]. The critical step of identifying metabolites or biomarkers is largely dependent on databases and existing literature. However, the substantial structural diversity of FBs and their metabolites, coupled with the scarcity of reference standards,

makes their precise identification and quantification a significant analytical challenge [4]. Furthermore, these compounds are often present in human biological fluids at very low concentrations [6], making the choice of appropriate sample preparation methods essential for their thorough investigation. It's also worth noting the often-unexpected chemical nature of FBs metabolites, stemming from the structural complexity of their precursors.

Among FBs, olive-derived products, such as olive oil and table olives, have been largely studied since they are closely tied to the Mediterranean diet. The consumption of these products has been strongly linked with increased life expectancy and protection against chronic and age-related conditions, including cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and neurodegenerative disorders [7–11]. Beyond their lipid content, olive products are rich in a group of relatively polar compounds known as olive phenols, olive polyphenols, or biophenols (OBs), which exhibit significant health benefits [12]. OBs are present in low concentrations in olive products and encompass a wide variety of chemical classes, including phenylalcohols, phenolic acids, secoiridoids, flavonoids, terpenoids, lignans, and hydroxy-isocromans (Fig. 1) [13]. Numerous studies have explored the effects of OBs on human health, and they are now being investigated for their influence on the human metabolome. A recent study showed that administering an olive-based supplement enriched with hydroxytyrosol (HT) over a six-month period had a notable impact on the urine metabolome, triggering specific biochemical pathways at both high (15 mg HT/day) and low (5 mg HT/day) doses, related to body weight as well as lipids' storage and distribution [14]. This underscores the importance of studying OBs bioavailability and metabolism in humans to better understand their biological and

Fig. 1. Representative chemical classes and compounds of olive oil and OBs.

pharmacological roles, focusing on metabolites identification [13].

Existing evidence suggests that, at least for the structurally simpler OBs, they are either absorbed in the small intestine—undergoing phase I and phase II transformations—or they reach the colon, where they are metabolized by gut microbiota through a range of enzymatic reactions [4,13]. However, due to the chemical diversity of OBs, their full biotransformation pathways have yet to be elucidated, and new precursor compounds continue to be identified (Fig. 1) [15]. Furthermore, most of their metabolites are not commercially available, limiting their use as reference standards for comprehensive identification and/or quantification. Consequently, their annotation often relies on proposed structures, hypotheses, and general knowledge of phase I and phase II metabolic reactions that are likely to occur *in vivo*.

Urine is the most commonly utilized biofluid in the case of FBs metabolism and, therefore, for OBs, in human metabolomic studies, investigating their impact of diet on health [16]. Urine offers the advantage of capturing temporal metabolic changes, providing indirect information on dietary exposure, and reflecting certain metabolic activities of gut microbiota [17]. Since urination is the body's primary route for excreting water-soluble waste, urine contains hundreds of metabolic end-products, offering a comprehensive overview of the human metabolome [16,18]. Additionally, urine holds distinct advantages over other biofluids in such studies. It allows for non-invasive sample collection in large volumes and at multiple time points [19, 20], and the diversity of chemical classes detectable in urine is extensive [21]. Moreover, urine is largely free from proteins and lipids that can interfere with analyses, while being rich in small-molecule metabolites [22].

However, urine also presents analytical challenges. It contains high concentrations of inorganic salts (chloride, sodium, potassium), urea, creatinine, ammonia, organic acids, and pigmented products from hemoglobin breakdown, all of which can complicate analysis and data processing [16]. The high salt concentration, in particular, can precipitate in chromatographic columns and interfere with electrospray ionization (ESI) or nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) probes, reducing analytical sensitivity and adding complexity to the optimization of experimental conditions [4,21]. Other challenges include the wide diversity of chemical structures, significant variation in metabolite concentration ranges, unpredictable dilution, and fluctuations in ionic strength, pH, and osmolality, all of which complicate the development of consistent and reproducible sample preparation methods [23].

Sample preparation—also referred to as sample treatment, clean-up, or extraction—is a crucial step in urine analysis and metabolomics studies. The main goals of sample preparation are to recover the analytes of interest from the urine matrix, remove interfering substances, enhance the analyte signal by increasing its concentration, and ensure robustness and reproducibility in the process. Selecting the most appropriate sample preparation method is especially critical given the complexity of the urine matrix, the vast heterogeneity of urine metabolites, and the low concentrations at which many, particularly FBs metabolites, are present [24,25]. Commonly, SPE SPME and QuEChERS, are employed when gas or liquid chromatography is implicated, as these techniques provide efficient extraction, purification, and concentration of target analytes, while minimizing matrix effects [22]. However, regardless of the automation, sensitivity, and precision these methods offer, the identification of metabolites remains putative in non-targeted profiling, particularly when reference standards are unavailable. An important requirement of any sample preparation method is its ability to recover target metabolites in a reproducible manner. In untargeted profiling methods, the sample pretreatment process is particularly crucial, as it ensures the recovery of a wide range of metabolites. This broad recovery is essential for a comprehensive interpretation of the results.

Regardless of whether the analysis is targeted or untargeted, various sample preparation techniques have been proposed for urine [4,22,23, 25–28]. When it comes to FBs and their metabolites in urine, they are

typically present in low concentrations, and their recovery from complex biological matrices is often limited, making detection and identification particularly challenging [29,30]. Moreover, the often lack of appropriate reference standards for more structurally complex or less abundant FBs adds another layer of difficulty, leading to the potentially vague or imprecise metabolite identification, especially common in untargeted urine metabolomics. Additionally, the absence of MS/MS fragmentation data and/or the use of low-resolution analyzers can result in incorrect metabolite identification. For instance, even simple compounds like HT, which is both an endogenous metabolite and abundant in foods, can be misidentified. HT (MW: 154.0629 g/mol) is difficult to distinguish from 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid (MW: 154.026611 g/mol), which shares the same molecular weight, but has a different molecular formula and fragmentation pattern, particularly when using low-resolution analyzers. Dubious annotations can also arise in FBs that have undergone common metabolic biotransformations such as methylation, glucuronidation, or sulfation, due to the lack of distinctive fragmentation patterns. For example, without a reference standard, it is nearly impossible to differentiate hydroxytyrosol-4'-glucuronide or sulfate from hydroxytyrosol-3'-glucuronide or sulfate.

To address these challenges, the parallel isolation of metabolites of interest in pure form presents a promising alternative for achieving unambiguous identification. Purification on milligrams scale would not only provide comprehensive spectral data from LC-MS as well as critical information such as chromatographic behavior and polarity, but also allow for 1 and 2D NMR experiments. To our knowledge, no existing clean-up method offers sufficient scalability for isolating FBs metabolites from human urine and at the same time cover a broad recovery of metabolites. Developing a workflow that meets both profiling and isolation requirements could significantly enhance the reliable identification of metabolites, enabling a direct link to their FBs precursor(s). This would help fill important gaps in understanding the bioavailability and metabolism of FBs.

Hence, the primary aim of this study was to develop a unified urine pretreatment workflow that is compatible with typical profiling set-ups and also allows for the isolation of biotransformation products and metabolites, contributing to their unambiguous identification. As a proof of concept, 24-h urine samples were collected daily for one month from a healthy male volunteer who got supplemented with a commercially available HT soft gel capsule (15 mg/day). Standard pre-treatment protocols for biological samples, such as liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) and solid phase extraction (SPE), were employed. Additionally, enrichment techniques, including macroporous adsorption resins (XAD-4, XAD-7, ion-exchange), were tested and compared. An innovative aspect of this approach was the application of methodologies typically used in natural product research, recognizing that FBs metabolites are modified natural products derived from metabolic downstream processes. For qualitative and semi-quantitative evaluation, all samples derived were analyzed using HPLC-DAD/ELSD, UPLC-HRMS, and NMR. Key parameters included chemical profile, extraction and recovery yield, metabolite richness, and specificity or selectivity based on the chemical classes of identified metabolites were considered. Ultimately, the proposed methodology was successfully applied for large-volume urine pretreatment, offering the potential for metabolite isolation. This enables accurate structural characterization of metabolites with high confidence, compensating for sensitivity limitations and allowing for the integration of other techniques like NMR. Extension of the current work will be involved in a future paper describing the separation, isolation and identification of OBs metabolites as well as their role in biochemical level through molecular pathways analysis (Part II). We believe that the proposed protocol will be valuable not only in traditional urine metabolomic studies, but also in cases where unambiguous identification of metabolites is crucial, particularly in the analysis of biochemical pathways and the investigation of FBs mechanisms of action within the framework of personalized nutrition.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and standards

Methanol (MeOH; Fisher Scientific, Loughborough, UK), ethyl acetate (EtOAc; Macron Fine Chemicals™ Leicestershire, England) and acetone (Merck, N. Jersey, US) used for urine extractions were of analytical grade. A Milli-Q-plus ultra-pure water system from Millipore (Milford, MA, US) was used to obtain the UPLC/HPLC water (H₂O) used during the analyses. XAD-type adsorbent resins (XAD-4; XAD-7HP; Amberlite; 20–60 mesh) were obtained from Merck SA (N. Jersey, USA), whereas Amberlite IR120 cation exchanger (hydrogen form) and Dowex 550A (hydroxide form) were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Supelco Discovery SPE cartridges (DSC-8, DSC-18, DSC-Si, LC-Diol) were purchased from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA) and Oasis HLB cartridges were acquired from Waters (Milliford, MA, US). Acetonitrile (ACN), H₂O and formic acid (FA) were used for HPLC-PDA profile analysis of different extraction systems were also HPLC grade (Fischer chemicals, Loughborough, UK). For UPLC-Orbitrap-MS analysis the used ACN and acetic acid were LC-MS grade (Fisher Chemical, Loughborough, UK). Deuterated water (D₂O) for NMR analysis was purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc. (Andover, MS, USA).

2.2. Collection and pre-processing of urine samples

In the current study, HT was supplemented in the form of a soft capsule for one month to a healthy male volunteer (38 years old) following a normal diet. The HT capsules were standardized in 2.5 mg HT/capsule. The chemical composition of the capsule is presented in detail in Fig. S1 and Table S1 (Supporting Information). 24 h urine samples were collected, as they are comprised of all voids, reducing the impact of any circadian variation and ensuring the presence of all metabolites excreted throughout the day [31]. In total 28 L of urine were collected over two weeks and pooled to achieve sample uniformity. Urine samples were transferred to the laboratory within the day and directly centrifuged at 3,500 rpm for 15 min. The pooled sample was aliquoted into 2 L containers and stored at –80 °C until further processing. Prior to storage or analysis, the selection of the most appropriate process to remove cellular debris and to minimize the effect of any contaminating bacteria was chosen. Based on literature, methods to minimize bacterial contamination that have been tested are pre-centrifugation, filtration, and treating the urine with additives (sodium azide, sodium fluoride, boric acid etc.) [31]. According to Saude and Skyes [20], Bernini et al. [32] and Ammerlaan et al. [33] pre-centrifugation at moderate speeds is effective at removing cellular debris and minimize bacterial contamination [31] and this methodology was chosen to be applied prior to samples storage. Regarding storage, according to the study of E.J. Saude and B.D. Sykes [20], urine storage in deep-freeze conditions (–80 °C) provided the best reflection of the original metabolite concentrations of urine. Additionally, storing samples at –80 °C prevents any metabolism of urinary metabolites by contaminating bacteria and has the additional benefit of not adding any chemicals to the sample itself, interfering with its final chemical composition [22,31,34,35] and thus, storage at –80 °C was selected for the storage of urine samples.

2.3. Urine pretreatment

2.3.1. Solid-phase extraction (SPE) protocols

Urine samples were thawed in ice, homogenized, and then centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C [31]. A 12-port model Visiprep solid phase extraction vacuum manifold from Supelco (Bellefonte, USA) was used for the SPE. The sorbents used in the present study can be divided into three categories: reversed-phase materials (e.g. DSC-18 and DSC-8), which use a nonpolar stationary phase such as the alkyl-bonded

silica; normal phase sorbents using a polar stationary phase such as silica with polar functional groups (e.g. DSC-Si, DSC-Diol) and Oasis HLB sorbent which is a hydrophilic-lipophilic-balanced, reversed-phase sorbent. Urine samples were cleaned up and preconcentrated using five different type-sorbent categories of SPE cartridges and 200 mL of urine were totally loaded per cartridge type utilizing the 12-port model Visiprep solid phase extraction device: P7. Discovery DSC-18 (500 mg/6 mL), P8. Discovery DSC-8 (500 mg/6 mL), and P9. Waters HLB (500 mg/6 mL), P10. Discovery DSC-Si (500 mg/6 mL), P11. Discovery DCS-Diol (500 mg/6 mL). Briefly, the cartridges were conditioned with 1.5 tube volumes of MeOH, followed by equilibration with 1.5 tube volumes of H₂O. Then, 6 mL of pooled urine was applied to the column, and the unretained fraction was discarded. The cartridges were subsequently washed with 1 tube volume of H₂O. The metabolites were afterwards eluted with 2 tube volumes of MeOH:H₂O (1:1 v/v), and 2 tube volumes of MeOH. The protocol was applied in triplicate. The elution fraction was evaporated to dryness using a Rotavapor® (Büchi) and stored at –80 °C until analysis. Three triplicates of each protocol were separately analyzed to verify the reproducibility of the experiment.

2.3.2. Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) protocols

Three different liquid-liquid extraction systems were tested: Urine/EtOAc (1:3 v/v) – P5, Urine/EtOAc/Acetone (1:2:1 v/v) – P6 and ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE, 45 min at 35 kHz), Urine/EtOAc (1:1 v/v) – P12. Extractions were carried out by mixing 200 mL of urine and the appropriate solvent system and the obtainment of the upper (organic) phase. More specifically, for P5 protocol, 200 mL of urine were mixed with 600 mL of EtOAc; for P6, 200 mL of urine were mixed with 400 mL of EtOAc and 200 mL of Acetone, while for P12, 200 mL of urine were mixed with 200 mL of EtOAc followed by UAE for 45 min at 35 kHz. The extractions were performed in triplicate to improve extraction efficiency. Supernatants were evaporated to dryness using a Rotavapor® (Büchi) and the dried samples were stored at –80 °C until analysis. Each LLE protocol was performed in triplicate.

2.3.3. Ion-exchange resins protocol

Urine underwent a desalting/treatment process based on the protocol developed by L. Whiley et al. [21] with some modifications. Briefly, 24 g of Amberlite IR120 resin exchanger resin (hydrogen form – cationic) was placed on an open column and pH was measured (pH = 2.24) to confirm the acidic conditions resulting from the release of hydrogen ions from the ion-exchange resin. Then, 3 column volumes of distilled water were passed through to wash the ion exchange resin followed by 2 column volumes of HCl (1 N), NaOH (1 N) and again HCl (1 N), successively. The resin was then washed again with distilled water. Next 200 mL of urine was loaded into the column and with a flow rate of 0.6–0.8 mL/min. Throughout the elution pH readings were taken to confirm the acidic conditions. After the first step the pH of urine was approximately 2. The eluate from the first step, was subsequently treated with the Aldrich Dowex Monosphere 550A (hydroxide form – anionic) anion-exchanger resin followed by pH determination (pH = 6.12) and titration with the additional anionic resin until neutral pH was achieved (resulting from the release of hydroxide ions). The protocol was applied in triplicate. The urine extract was removed at this point and was evaporated to dryness using rotavapor and stored at –80 °C until analysis (protocol P3). Finally, a combined protocol including the use of ion exchange resins followed by a second step involving treatment with the XAD-4 resin was tested (P4).

2.3.4. Adsorption resins protocols

Two adsorption resins, which are used to retain small molecules, XAD-4 (P1) and XAD-7 (P2), and previously described by E Tuenter et al. [28], to eliminate sugars from chocolate products were tested with some adjustments. In more detail, 70 g of Amberlite XAD-4 or XAD-7 resin was placed in a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask and washed with 3 column volumes of H₂O, 2 column volumes of MeOH and then again with 3 column

volumes of H₂O for equilibration. 200 mL of urine was mixed with XAD-4 or XAD-7 resin, stirred for 3 h and then decanted. The resin was washed with 2 column volumes of H₂O to remove residual urine and unfavorable compounds, and afterwards recovery of metabolites was performed with 2 column volumes of MeOH. The column volume for XAD-4 was calculated to $V = 233 \text{ mL}$ ($r = 30 \text{ mm}$, $L = 330 \text{ mm}$), while for XAD-7 the column volume was calculated $V = 240 \text{ mL}$ ($r = 30 \text{ mm}$, $L = 340 \text{ mm}$). The protocol was applied in triplicate. The collected MeOH extract was then dried using Rotavapor® (Büchi) and stored at $-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis. Each extraction was performed in triplicate.

2.4. Urine profiling and analysis

2.4.1. HPLC-DAD/ELSD experimental parameters

Chromatographic analysis was performed on an Agilent HPLC 1260 Infinity II system (Santa Clara, United States), equipped with a 1260 Infinity II Quaternary pump, an autosampler with a thermostat, a column compartment, and a 1260 Infinity II Diode Array Detector (DAD), as well, a 1260 Infinity II Evaporative Light Scattering Detector (ELSD). Metabolites were monitored at 210, 235, 254, 280 and 366 nm, and UV spectra were recorded between 190 and 600 nm as well as on ELSD. Separation was performed on a Supelco Discovery HS RP C18 column ($150 \text{ mm} \times 4.6 \text{ mm i.d.}$, $5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particle size) from Sigma-Aldrich at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ equipped with a matching pre-column. The injection volume was $20 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$. The mobile phases consisted of a gradient system with H₂O and 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid as solvent A, and ACN with 0.1 % (v/v) FA as solvent B. The flow rate was set at 1.0 mL/min and total analysis time was 53 min. Separation was achieved under the following gradient conditions: 2 % B at the first 2 min, afterwards B reached 100 % in 40 min and stayed stable for 5 min. At the 48th minute the system returned to the initial conditions for 5 min for system equilibrium. The evaporator temperature of ELSD was $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the nebulized temperature was $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, while the nitrogen flow rate was set at 1.60 ml/min . Data processing was performed with the Agilent OpenLab CDS software.

2.4.2. UPLC-ESI(±)-HRMS (Orbitrap) experimental parameters

Urine profiling was performed on an Acquity UPLC System (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled to a hybrid LTQ-Orbitrap Discovery Mass Spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The mass spectrometer was equipped with electrospray ionization (ESI) source and operated in negative and positive ion mode. The extracts were analyzed with an LC gradient consisting of H₂O with 0.1 % (v/v) FA (solvent A) and ACN (solvent B). The elution method started with 5 % of B which stayed 1 min. In the next 13 min B reached 100 % and stayed for 2 min. Finally, at 17.5 min, the system returned to the initial conditions and stayed for 2.5 min for system equilibration. A Supelco Ascentis Express C18 ($100 \times 2.1 \text{ mm i.d.}$, $2.7 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ particle size) column was used for the separation, with a stable temperature of $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The measurements were performed with a total acquisition time of 20 min and a flow rate of $400 \text{ }\mu\text{L/min}$. The injection volume was $10 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ and the autosampler temperature was at $7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The mass spectra data were acquired in the full scan m/z range of 115–1000, in negative and positive mode at a resolving power of 30,000 and data-dependent MS/MS events were acquired, using an electrospray ionization source (ESI). The mass range for MS/MS experiments was set to m/z 113–1000. In both modes, the data-dependent acquisition was simultaneously performed using a collision induced dissociation C-trap (CID) with normalized collision energy at 35 V and a mass resolution of 15,000. In negative mode capillary temperature was set to $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the source voltage was 2.7 kV. Tube lens and capillary voltage were respectively tuned at -100 V and -30 V . In positive mode capillary temperature was set to $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the source voltage was 3.60 kV. Tube lens and capillary voltage were respectively tuned at $+120 \text{ V}$ and $+40 \text{ V}$. Data acquisition, and the spectral interpretation was performed using the Xcalibur™ (Version 2.2, Thermo Scientific) software. Specifically, for identification and dereplication the following ranking criteria were employed: retention time (RT), elemental composition

(EC), $10 \leq \text{RDBeq} \leq 20$, mass range m/z 100–1000 Da, mass tolerance $\leq 5 \text{ ppm}$; HRMS/MS spectra of the selected peaks and identification of the fragmentation pattern and literature.

2.4.3. NMR analysis

6 mg of each urine extract were reconstituted in $600 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ D₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, Canada) containing phosphate buffer solution and 0.05 % (w/v) of sodium-3-(trimethylsilyl)-[2,2,3,3-2H₄]-1-propionate (TSP, Armar Chemicals, Switzerland) as internal standard, for chemical shift calibration, adopting the methodology that has been proposed by C. Xiao et al. [36]. The addition of the buffer solution is necessary since there is a large variation of salt concentration and pH in urine. The buffer system was prepared in D₂O containing TSP (0.05 %, w/v) for pH control of the human urine samples, namely, potassium sodium buffer solutions (with final concentration of 1.5 M and, pH 7.4) with K₂HPO₄ and NaH₂PO₄ (molar ratio of 4:1). Then, the samples were vortexed and sonicated to completely dissolve the urine extract and the samples were transferred into 5 mm tubes for NMR analysis. 1D (¹H) and 2D NMR experiments (JRES, HSQC) for structure elucidation were performed on a 600 MHz Bruker Avance III spectrometer (Bruker Biospin GmbH, Rheinstetten, Germany) equipped with a 5-mm PABBI 1H/D-BB inverse detection probe with a z-gradient. ¹H NMR spectra were acquired with 128 scans at 305 K (proton frequency of 600.113 MHz, B₀ = 14.1 T) using an 1D NOESY pulse sequence with saturation of the water resonance (Bruker's pulse program noesygppr1d). Experiments were conducted with the IconNMR suite by Bruker and the help of a 60-place sample changer (B-ACS-60). Parameters for acquisition were as follows: number of scans, 128; $\pi/2$ pulse, $\sim 8 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$, time domain (TD), 64 k data points; acquisition time, 3.9 s; relaxation delay, 2 s; and spectral width, 8417.509 Hz. An exponential multiplication window function with a line-broadening factor (lb) of 0.3 Hz was applied on the free induction decay (FID) to obtain the final spectra. For 2D NMR experiments, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were acquired at 600.11 MHz and 150.91 MHz, respectively. Chemical shifts (δ) are expressed in ppm while coupling constants (J) in Hz. The spectral width was set at 14 ppm. ¹H and ¹³C shifts were referenced to TSP, whilst evaluation of the spectra was carried out using MestreNova 6.1.1 software and TopSpin software version 3.5 (Bruker BioSpin GmbH, Germany). Manual phase and baseline correction were applied to all spectra. The multiplicity of vertices is expressed as s (singlet), brs (broad singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), dd (doublet of doublets) and m (multiplet). The metabolite assignment was achieved using literature data and confirmed by 2D NMR spectroscopy experiments.

2.5. Metabolite identification workflow

Initially, UPLC–HRMS chromatograms and their corresponding full scan HRMS spectra were investigated. The ion extraction method (XICS) was used in parallel with peak-to-peak selection to obtain the corresponding full-scan spectra. The Xcalibur™ (Version 2.2, Thermo Scientific) software calculator tool was used for the proposed elemental composition (EC) calculation. The following criteria were used: mass tolerance $\leq 5 \text{ ppm}$, $0 \leq \text{RDBeq} \leq 20$, Isotopes: ¹²C (min 0 – max 30, mass 12.000), ¹H (min 0 – max 60, mass 1.008), ¹⁶O (min 0 – max 20, mass 15.995), ¹⁴N (min 0 – max 15, mass 14.003), ³²S (min 0 – max 10, mass 31.972), ³⁵Cl (min 0 – max 10, mass 34.969), ²³Na (min 0 – max 5, mass 22.990), ³⁹K (min 0 – max 5, mass 38.969). For dereplication/annotation the following chromatographic and spectrometric features were considered: retention time (Rt), suggested elemental composition (EC), $10 \leq \text{RDBeq} \leq 20$, mass range m/z 100–1000 Da, mass tolerance $\leq 5 \text{ ppm}$; HRMS/MS spectra of the selected peaks and identification of the fragmentation pattern and literature as thoroughly described by J. Tchoumtchoua et al. [37]. Moreover, HRMS/MS spectra contributed to the identification of specific chemical features based on in-house databases. In addition, online databases were used for further structural information, more specifically: Human Metabolome Data Base (HMDB)

(<http://www.hmdb.ca/>), Urine Metabolome Database (<https://urinemetabolome.ca/>), METLIN Metabolomics Database (<https://metlin.scripps.edu/>) and ChemSpider chemical structure database (<http://www.chemspider.com/>). Maximum mass deviation of ± 5 ppm between theoretical and experimental was set as a threshold for parent ions while product ions must not exceed the maximum mass deviation of ± 10 ppm. To proceed with robust metabolite annotations the structure of identified compounds from UPLC-HRMS/MS spectra were also investigated with NMR spectra analysis. The NMR data were compared with those previously reported in literature and Reaxys database (<http://www.reaxys.com/>) and in-house measurements when compounds were available.

2.6. Urine extraction in large scale

For the recovery of urinary minor metabolites, it was deemed necessary to test the most promising extraction methodologies for their effectiveness at a higher scale (6 L of urine). More specifically, the three protocols that showed the optimal results, i.e. liquid-liquid extraction Urine/EtOAc (1:3 v/v) and the use of XAD-7 or XAD-4 resins, were evaluated for their effectiveness. The procedure followed was the same as that applied in the lab scale (P1, P2 & P5).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Experimental design and methods

At the core of the current study is the development and application of an effective urine-specific sample preparation methodology, targeting FB metabolites with large-scale potential, and designed to facilitate both profiling and isolation. This dual-purpose workflow is compared with standard as well as alternative clean-up methods. Specifically, twelve different sample preparation protocols commonly used in urine analysis—such as LLE and SPE—were evaluated alongside additional methods typically used in natural product research for complex mixtures, such as resin-based approaches. As a proof of concept, urine samples from a subject supplemented with HT were utilized. Previous studies have shown that daily HT consumption at doses exceeding 5 mg/day (two capsules) significantly impacts the urine metabolome [14]. To achieve a final dosage of 15 mg HT/day, a healthy volunteer received two capsules three times a day for one month. Moreover, the capsules were analyzed to verify the HT concentration (Fig. S1, Supplementary). After two weeks of supplementation, 24-h urine samples were collected daily for two weeks, providing sufficient material for both lab-scale trials and subsequent upscaling.

Beyond targeting HT metabolites following supplementation, the broader objective was to develop an unbiased sample preparation protocol suitable for urine profiling studies, maximizing coverage of various metabolic pathways and accommodating the wide heterogeneity of analytes. To achieve this, specific parameters were established to monitor and evaluate the entire process. Key areas of focus included (i) minimizing or eliminating endogenous interfering compounds in the extracted samples, (ii) prioritizing the analytes of interest, (iii) monitoring chemical representation of metabolites and (iv) reducing time-consuming steps in the procedure [4,26].

Solid-phase extraction (SPE) is a widely used methodology in plasma and urine analysis, particularly in metabolomics, as it allows for the design of highly selective protocols [38]. SPE works on affinity-based separations, where analytes of interest are separated by adsorption onto a solid sorbent, with the elution protocol playing a critical role. Key parameters such as the stationary phase, sample volume, solvent system, pH, and modifier content are typically optimized to minimize matrix effects and achieve selective elution of the target analytes [4,36,39,40]. In contrast, liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) is primarily considered an enrichment methodology based on the partitioning of analytes between two immiscible liquids, where analytes are extracted according to their

relative solubility in each phase [41]. This process involves vigorous mixing, followed by phase separation, often assisted by centrifugation, to transfer the analytes into the desired phase [4,41]. LLE has been extensively employed for extracting phenols and polyphenols from major dietary sources [4,22,42].

An enrichment methodology commonly used in natural product research is the application of macroporous adsorption resins (XAD-4, XAD-7), which have been successfully employed to recover phenolic derivatives from various substrates [43–47]. XAD resins are typically used to adsorb organic substances from aqueous systems and polar solvents. Given urine's challenging matrix, due to its high inorganic salt content, its liquid nature makes it suitable for resin-based treatment. Amberlite XAD-4 and XAD-7 are non-ionic, crosslinked polymers with large surface areas and 'moderately polar' properties, often used to remove relatively polar compounds. Additionally, ion-exchange resins are widely used in purification and decontamination processes, as they trap ions within their porous structures. In this study, we examined the performance of Amberlite IR-120, a gel-type, strongly acidic cation-exchange resin (sulfonated polystyrene), and Dowex Monosphere 550A (hydroxide form, Sigma-Aldrich), an anion-exchange resin. New-generation sample preparation techniques, such as solid-phase microextraction, liquid-phase microextraction, and dispersive microsolid-phase extraction, were considered unsuitable for large-volume urine pretreatment protocols and were therefore excluded from our experimental design.

For better interpretation, the resulting extracts were categorized into three groups: resins (P1–P4), LLE (P5–P6), and SPE (P7–P11), as detailed in Table 1, along with specific evaluation parameters for each protocol. Extraction yield was a key consideration, as it must be sufficient to meet the sensitivity requirements of NMR analysis, which is known for its limitations in this regard. Additionally, the number of metabolites is critical for ensuring comprehensive metabolome coverage. The method also needed to be non-specific to certain chemical classes, allowing for the representation of diverse metabolic and biochemical pathways essential for further investigation and pathway analysis. Lastly, practical factors such as simplicity, cost-effectiveness, efficiency, speed, and reproducibility were also considered.

3.2. Extraction yield

A crucial factor in sample preparation, regardless of the substrate, is the extraction yield, as it is directly linked to both the qualitative and quantitative recovery of the analytes of interest. Fig. 2 illustrates the extraction yields obtained from the various sample preparation protocols. These yields ranged widely, from 0.09 to 12.56 g/L of urine extract. In general, resin-based methods resulted in the highest overall

Table 1
Sample pre-treatments, sorbents and solvents and sample coding.

Method	Sorbent/solvents	Sample coding
Adsorption	Adsorption resin XAD-4	P1
	Adsorption resins XAD-7	P2
Ion exchange	Dowex Monosphere 550A (anion exchange) & Amberlite IR120 (cation exchange) resins	P3
Adsorption & Ion exchange	Ion exchange & XAD-4	P4
LLE	Urine/EtOAc (1:3 v/v)	P5
	Urine/EtOAc/Acetone (1:2:1 v/v)	P6
	Urine/EtOAc (1:1 v/v), UAE	P12
SPE	RP C18	P7
	RP C8	P8
	HLB (Oasis)	P9
	NP Si	P10
	NP Diol	P11

Fig. 2. Extraction yields of the employed urine sample preparation protocols. Results are expressed in g of urine extract per 1 L of urine (g/L). Blue bars represent the adsorption resin protocols, the yellow bar the liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) and the green bars the protocols with SPE cartridges. *The extraction yields for the ion exchange resins (P3) and LLE protocols urine/EtOAc/Acetone (P6) are separately illustrated due to much higher scale. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

recovery, followed by LLE, and lastly, SPE. In order of effectiveness, the extraction protocols ranked as follows: **P3**>**P6**>>**P2**>**P1**>**P5**>**P7**-**P8**-**P11**-**P9**>**P4**-**P10**. Notably, ion exchange resins (**P3**) and the LLE system using urine/EtOAc/Acetone (1:2:1 v/v) (**P6**) yielded the highest values. However, the significantly higher yields raised concerns about the potential recovery of unwanted salts or other interfering compounds. The next highest yield was observed with XAD-7 resins (**P2**) at 2.17 g/L, followed by XAD-4 resins (**P1**) and LLE with the urine/EtOAc (1:3 v/v) system (**P5**), which produced 1.77 g/L and 1.74 g/L, respectively. SPE cartridges (**P7**-**P11**) showed the lowest recoveries, as did the combined use of ion exchange and XAD-4 resins (**P4**). Additionally, while ultrasound-assisted LLE (**P12**) was tested, the formation of a strong emulsion prevented further evaluation of this method.

The low yield observed with SPE is consistent with the literature since it is almost completely adjusted to small urine volumes and LC-UV, -DAD or -MS analysis, on-line and off-line [4,38,42]. Regarding LLE, standard solvents mixtures e.g. (ACN, DCM, MeOH, EtOAc, etc.) mixed with additives (buffer, acids, or bases) are usually employed and the yield is highly related to the scope of the study (targeted or untargeted) while some constraints exist due to low solvent options to satisfy the necessary creation of the biphasic system and the common presence of emulsions affecting repeatability [4,41]. In respect to ion exchange resins, they are less commonly employed in metabolite profiling studies despite their efficiency due to formation of salts and the multi-step procedure required. They are mainly used for the recovery of certain molecules from urine (e.g. ionized compounds) and the information about the yield are not commonly given [21]. Finally, regarding the adsorption resins XAD-4 or XAD-7, there is no information reported so far for the treatment of urine to our knowledge.

3.3. Determination and evaluation of recovered metabolites

The next step involved the metabolite profiling of the produced extracts, focusing on the number of identified metabolites and the representation of various chemical classes. Special emphasis was placed on recovering OBs and phenolic urine metabolites, while also ensuring a comprehensive reflection of urine metabolome. To achieve this, the extracts were analyzed in parallel using HPLC-DAD/ELSD, LC-HRMS, and NMR, each providing complementary insights for thorough

metabolite representation. LC-HRMS, with its high sensitivity, was critical for detecting minor metabolites and offering structural information through HRMS and HRMS/MS data. NMR, employing 1 and 2D experiments, significantly enhanced identification confidence while providing direct quantitative information. Meanwhile, the hyphenation of HPLC with DAD and ELSD detectors yielded valuable data, including the detection of non-UV-absorbing compounds and key chromatographic properties such as polarity and peak shape. Thus, the identification of metabolites was achieved based on complimentary information from the different platforms employed offering additional confidence to the identification process. Chromatograms for all extracts are provided in supplementary information (Figs. S2–S24), with comparative LC-MS and NMR data shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

As presented in Fig. 3, it is evident that the urine profiles vary significantly depending on the sample preparation method used. Normal-phase SPE (**P10**, **P11**) is not an ideal choice for urine treatment, as only a few metabolites were detected, which is expected given the overall high polarity of urine metabolites. Similar conclusions can be drawn from the ¹H NMR and HPLC-DAD/ELSD data (Supporting Information, Figs. S11-12, S23-24, & S59-66). Equally poor results were obtained from the **P3** extract treated with anion- and cation-exchange resins. While a slightly richer profile was observed in the ¹H NMR and HPLC-DAD/ELSD data, it remained relatively limited (SI, Figs. S4, S16, S30-30). The strong ion suppression effect, likely due to the presence of inorganic substances and salts, suggests that an additional desalting step may be necessary, particularly before LC-MS analysis. For the three extracts derived from reversed phase SPE (**P7**, **P8**, **P9**), the metabolite profiles were very similar, with only quantitative differences. It is worth noting, however, that medium-polarity metabolites ($R_t = 6\text{--}11$ min) were favored, while polar metabolites ($R_t = 1\text{--}6$ min) were significantly underestimated (SI, Figs. S8-10 & S20-22). Despite this, the high performance of these extracts in HPLC-DAD/ELSD and UPLC-HRMS analyses supports their regular use in metabolomics studies, particularly SPE cartridges with C18 and HLB, which are widely employed due to the versatility of their stationary phases. Nevertheless, their recovery efficiency and limited sample capacity restrict their application on a larger scale for isolation purposes. In contrast, extracts **P1**, **P2**, and **P4** (treated with adsorption resins or a combination of methods) exhibited the opposite profile, favoring the recovery of polar compounds (SI, Figs. S2-

Fig. 3. Comparison of representative UPLC-ESI(-)-HRMS base peak chromatograms (BPC) of the derived extracts (**P1-P12**) in negative mode. In the first chromatogram, the elution gradient is schematically represented as a % percentage of organic solvent B (ACN) in relation to analysis time (min). The polarity of eluted metabolites is also annotated.

5, S14-15 & S17). Sequential treatment with ion exchange resins followed by adsorption resins appeared to improve the overall profile, likely due to the removal of ion-suppressing molecules, which enhanced LC-MS detection. While there were some differences between the resins, these were primarily quantitative. **P2** demonstrated the best profile in HPLC-DAD analysis (Fig. S3), followed by **P5** (Fig. S6). In comparison, **P1** showed fewer peaks and lower peak resolution, likely due to the higher recovery of polar compounds. Regarding the two LLE methods (**P5** and **P6**), they both displayed qualitative and quantitative differences. The addition of acetone (**P6**) did not optimize partitioning and separation, making the simpler urine/EtOAc system (**P5**) more effective, as it yielded a richer profile (SI, Fig. S6-7, S18-19).

Notably, **P5** provided the best representation of metabolites across different polarities, capturing both polar and medium-polarity compounds. Further analysis in positive mode (see SI, Tables S3–13) revealed additional insights. Since positive mode is generally more complex and crowded compared to negative mode, non-polar SPE sorbents (**P7**, **P8**, **P9**) were more compatible, offering the highest number of detected metabolites. XAD-7 (**P2**) proved more efficient than XAD-4 (**P1**), while ion exchange resins (**P3**), a combination of resins (**P4**), and polar SPE sorbents (**P10** and **P11**) performed similarly to their results in negative mode. Detailed lists of identified metabolites per protocol are given in supplementary information (Tables, S3 to S13).

The LC-MS results indicate that relying solely on a single analytical method is insufficient to consistently and reliably characterize the metabolome of complex mixtures like urine, despite its exceptional sensitivity. Therefore, the next step involved analyzing the same samples with NMR, where compound detection depends exclusively on molar concentration and the analysis is chemically unbiased. In Fig. 4, the ^1H NMR spectra (600 MHz, D_2O) of all extracts are presented. The similarity among the three reversed phase SPE methods (C-8/**P7**, C18/**P8**, HLB/**P9**) is confirmed, as is the resemblance between the two normal phase SPE methods (Si/**P10**, Diol/**P11**).

Additionally, **P3** (resins) again displayed a poor metabolite profile. Regarding the adsorption resins (**P1** and **P2**), they appeared to retain metabolites well, providing a rich profile with a broad representation of molecules, as indicated by the spin systems covering both high and low fields. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **P5** seems the richest in detected metabolites, showing also the higher number of signals downfield in the area where aromatic and phenolic protons are resonated (SI, Figs. S38-42). This observation together with the respective results from LC-MS, -UV/ELSD analysis renders **P5** the most promising method for the recovery of the higher number of OBs metabolites. All the ^1H NMR spectra are presented in Figs. S26-68 with the respective assignment of compounds.

A detailed analysis, combining identification data from both LC-HRMS/MS and NMR platforms (SI, Table S2), indicates that protocols **P1**, **P2**, and **P5** resulted in the highest number of identified metabolites (LC-MS/NMR: 83/59, 90/62 and 81/69, respectively) while **P3**, **P10**, and **P11** had the lowest (LC-MS/NMR 20/28, 27/26 and 25/29, respectively). These findings suggest that XAD-4, XAD-7, and LLE (urine/EtOAc, 1:1) are the most suitable for comprehensive urine profiling. Additionally, these same protocols showed superior extraction yields, supporting their potential for upscaling (Fig. 5). Taking into account factors like effort, time, safety and cost, **P5** appears to be the optimal choice for urine treatment prior to analysis and/or metabolite isolation (Fig. 5 and Supplementary Table S2).

For **P5**, 69 metabolites were assigned with ^1H NMR, of which 45 % were also identified with UPLC-HRMS. To delve deeper into the chemistry of recovered compounds, the identified metabolites were classified based on their chemical class. Specifically, i) carboxylic acids as products of various metabolic pathways (citric acid, lactic acid, uric acid etc), ii) amino acids, peptides and amines, iii) phenols and phenolic acids directly associated with FB metabolism (including gut microbiota metabolism), iv) indoles and derivatives (products of tryptophan metabolism and microbial biotransformation), v) nucleotides and

Fig. 4. Superimposed ^1H NMR spectra of all extracts P1-P11 (600 MHz, D_2O).

Fig. 5. Radar plot of the parameters used for the evaluation of the different methods (Left): Illustration of the chemical classes of identified urine compounds and pie chart indicating the percentage of exogenous (xenobiotics) and endogenously produced compounds (Right). *in cases of dual origin the metabolites are classified based on the main route.

nucleosides, vi) fatty acids and esters, vii) steroids, viii) xenobiotics including drugs, environmental toxins and their metabolites (e.g. pain killers metabolites) and ix) miscellaneous. The classification was based on the categorization proposed by the literature [16] and the HMDB database. In the present study the sugars and vitamins were not taken into account since are not classified as FBs.

As described in Fig. 5, phenols, phenolic acids and derivatives represent the major chemical class of identified compounds (41) followed by commonly found urine metabolites and xenobiotics belonging to pyridines and pyrimidines (e.g. nicotinamide, nicotinic acid), purines (mainly xanthenes e.g. uric acid), fatty acids (FAs) and esters (mainly carnitines), benzoic acids (e.g. hippuric acid) and carboxylic acids as well as indole derivatives and nucleotides. It is worth noting that from the identified compounds more than half (57 %) are compounds or their metabolites originated from diet or generally xenobiotics including drugs (pain killers) metabolites. A detailed list of identified metabolites in each extract (P1-P11) is included in supplementary material. The

group of phenolics attracted more of our attention since it is directly associated with the supplementation with HT and generally OBs.

It is important to note here that HT is also produced from human organisms from catecholamines (dopamine) pathway, but the main source is food products. In more detail, throughout the analysis of spectroscopic and spectrometric data numerous compounds were identified belonging to HT and tyrosol (T) as well as their metabolites such as glucuronide, sulfate and acetate forms. Moreover, catabolic products of HT and T were identified through phase I and II metabolism as well as by gut microbiome activity. Further and more detailed information about these OBs metabolites will be presented in part II of this work. As shown in the radar plot (Fig. 5) comparing the different protocols, P3, P4, P6, and P10 are directly excluded due to significant underperformance in one of the four evaluated factors. Regarding metabolite identification, LC-MS generally outperforms NMR, though identification with LC-MS is often putative. Detailed results for each protocol are available in supplementary information (SI, Table S2). It is worth mentioning that

Fig. 6. Comparison of the different sample preparation methods (P1-P11) in respect to the biochemical pathways they are involved or originated from and number of identified recovered metabolites. Emphasis is given to phenolics and gut microbiome metabolites.

generally the LLE protocols with or without resins afforded higher number of metabolites compared to those including sorbents like SPE. Also, more than half of the identified metabolites are xenobiotics, with a significant proportion originating from dietary sources, highlighting the value of urine for metabolism studies.

The final component of this study was to assess the identified compounds based on their involvement in certain biochemical pathways and in relation to the sample preparation method used for their recovery. The goal was to investigate any bias related to sample pretreatment which could lead to inaccurate results and conclusions. In Fig. 6, the identified compounds are categorized and displayed as a colored bar graph based on the recovery method (P1-P11). This includes both fundamental pathways, such as amino acids, pyrimidine, purine, and bile acids, as well as more specialized metabolic processes like tyrosine, tryptophan, creatine/creatinine, caffeine, and nicotines metabolism. The compounds associated with phenolic metabolites (teal bar), those linked to the tyrosine pathway (pink bar), and those related to microbial catabolism (light purple bar) were emphasized and evaluated separately, as they are particularly relevant to OBs. Therefore, those three groups could be counted also to determine specificity in the sample treatment method. It is evident that, despite the number of metabolites identified, there is a high discrepancy between the different methods. As in previous assessments, P3 (Ion exchange), P10 and P11 (normal phase SPE) are considerably inferior with some pathways being underrepresented. As far as the methods employing reversed phase SPE (P7, P8 and P9), the performance is similar and only minor differences are observed, e.g. in tyrosine metabolism and gut microbiota biotransformation products. Despite being the most used method, the number of recovered metabolites is poorer compared to methods employing resins (P1, P2, P4) and LLE (P5). Regarding P6, it shows a close performance to P5 considering the biochemical aspect, however as mentioned already it suffers from a low number of recovered compounds. The most important outcome of the specific assessment is that P1, P2 and P5 continue to supercede without showing any limitations in respect to selectivity or specificity towards certain groups of compounds. Discrepancies between the methods in favor of specific pathways could lead to misleading results towards to comprehensive illustration of urine metabolome, evaluation of possible biomarkers or even hypothesis of biochemical and biological role. Further details of this will be provided in part II of this manuscript. Based on these data, it is clear how crucial sample pretreatment is prior to analysis, especially when pathway analysis is intended.

Based on the consolidated findings, P1, P2, and P5 are identified as the most suitable and efficient methods for urine treatment prior to analysis. These methods recover a broad range of metabolites without bias toward specific chemical classes, enabling more comprehensive and unbiased data interpretation. Additionally, they demonstrate high extraction yields, making them well-suited for upscaling. Of the three, P5 stands out as the most optimal choice, as it is simpler, less labor-intensive, more cost-effective, and directly compatible with upscaling for metabolite isolation and precise structure elucidation.

3.4. Large-scale urine extraction

As mentioned already, an objective of the current effort is to feature a sample preparation method for urine extraction which could be efficient, but also scalable for the purification and *de novo* structural elucidation of FBs metabolites. Achieving a balance between high recoveries for the majority of analytes and maintaining the extract's cleanliness is crucial [27].

The recovery of urine metabolites in a sufficient quantity to enable complete spectroscopic characterization, as well the evaluation of their biochemical role and biological activity (*in vitro* and *in vivo* models) requires the extraction and preconcentration and of a large volume of urine. Towards this concept, the best performing protocols i.e. XAD-4 (P1), XAD-7 (P2) resins and LLE urine/EtOAc (1:3 v/v) (P5) were

applied in large-scale extraction of urine samples (6 L per protocol). The parameters of yield and number (and type) of recovered metabolites were re-evaluated to elicit the most effective extraction methodology. P2 protocol showed higher extraction yield (12.84 g) relative to P1 and P5 (10.83 g and 11.52 g, respectively).

Additionally, P2 was found to be the most effective in the removal of interfering substances such as proteins and lipids, while the number of recovered metabolites is a little higher. On the other hand, P5 provided also high recovery and was advantageous in applicability parameters since it is significantly shorter, with operational simplicity and repeatability (SI, Tables S3, S6 & Figs. S25, S68). However, although P5 protocol shows a slightly lower extraction yield compared to P2, we consider that it has an advantage in all other criteria considered in this study, i.e. minimizing endogenous interfering compounds, simplicity, as well as reducing the time-consuming steps in the procedure. Furthermore, the significantly shorter sample preparation allows the minimization of metabolite degradation, which is an important pre-analytical variable for quantitative bioanalysis in biological matrices [41]. In Fig. 7, all assigned metabolites in P5 are annotated using 1 and 2D NMR experiments.

4. Conclusions

The primary objective of this study was to develop a unified urine preparation workflow that meets profiling requirements, while facilitating the isolation of urine metabolites and their unambiguous structure elucidation. Emphasis was given on FBs metabolites, which are characterized by high chemical variability, necessitating much effort for confident identification. To achieve this goal, twelve different urine extraction protocols were compared and accompanied by detailed metabolite identification i.e. standard methods like SPE and LLE were evaluated alongside resins (ion exchange and adsorption) commonly used in the natural products field for enrichment purposes. To enhance identification confidence and metabolite coverage the evaluation was conducted using a combination of HPLC-DAD/ELSD, LC-ESI(±)-HRMS/MS, and 1 & 2D NMR techniques. Key parameters such as extraction yield, number of identified metabolites, as well as aspects which are commonly overlooked, like metabolites chemical classifications, and associated biochemical pathways were assessed. Based on the results, adsorption resins XAD-4, XAD-7, and LLE with Urine/EtOAc (1:3, v/v) proved superior across all evaluated criteria. Furthermore, detailed identification of metabolites was performed based on the methods used highlighting the necessity of complimentary analysis for complete outcomes. To this end, the highest performing methods were further tested in an upscaling process with larger urine volumes, confirming their effectiveness. XAD-7 stood out for its ability to remove unwanted compounds, capture a high number of metabolites, and provide broad coverage, while LLE [Urine/EtOAc (1:3, v/v)] was highlighted for its simplicity, ease of use, and cost-efficiency. The proposed workflows are versatile and can be applied to various urine analysis applications, offering the added benefit of enabling the preparative isolation and precise structure elucidation of urine metabolites. This is particularly valuable for FBs metabolites, which are present in low concentrations and exhibit significant structural diversity. A detailed and accurate description of the urine metabolome can substantially contribute to the study and interpretation of biochemical pathways related to FBs found in foods, a crucial factor in investigating the impact of diet on human health and disease prevention. This method holds promise for applications in precision nutrition monitoring, such as predicting the effects of the Mediterranean diet through metabolic characteristics. Extension of this work including isolation, identification and pathways analysis of FBs metabolites will be presented in Part II of this work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evangelos Kalampokis: Writing – review & editing, Writing –

Fig. 7. Assignment of ¹H NMR signals of urine metabolites after treatment with LLE-protocol P5.

original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Theodora Nikou**: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stavros Beteinakis**: Visualization, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maria Halabalaki**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01 “GreenCosmIn” project (project code 101131346) for the financial support.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2025.343947>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Bayram, A. González-Sarriás, G. Ista, M. Garcia-Aloy, C. Morand, K. Tuohy, R. García-Villalba, P. Mena, Breakthroughs in the health effects of plant food bioactives: a perspective on microbiomics, nutri(epi)genomics, and metabolomics, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 66 (2018) 10686–10692, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.8b03385>.
- S.V. Luca, I. Macovei, A. Bujor, A. Miron, K. Skalicka-Woźniak, A.C. Aprotosoia, A. Trifan, Bioactivity of dietary polyphenols: the role of metabolites, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 60 (2020) 626–659, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2018.1546669>.
- M. Marhuenda-muñoz, E.P. Laveriano-santos, A. Tresserra-rimbau, R.M. Lamuela-Raventós, Miriam Vallverdú-Quera Martínez-Huélamo, A. Microbial phenolic metabolites: which molecules actually have an effect on human health? *Nutrients* 11 (2019) 1–15.
- A. López-Yerena, I. Domínguez-López, A. Vallverdú-Queralt, M. Pérez, O. Jáuregui, E. Escribano-Ferrer, R.M. Lamuela-Raventós, Metabolomics technologies for the identification and quantification of dietary phenolic compound metabolites: an overview, *Antioxidants* 10 (2021) 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox10060846>.
- G. Theodoridis, H. Gika, D. Raftery, R. Goodacre, R.S. Plumb, I.D. Wilson, Ensuring Fact-Based Metabolite Identification in Liquid Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry-Based Metabolomics, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.2c05192>.
- E.P. Laveriano-Santos, M. Marhuenda-Muñoz, A. Vallverdú-Queralt, M. Martínez-Huélamo, A. Tresserra-Rimbau, E. Miliarakis, C. Arancibia-Riveros, O. Jáuregui, A. M. Ruiz-León, S. Castro-Baquero, et al., Identification and quantification of urinary microbial phenolic metabolites by HPLC-ESI-LTQ-orbitrap-HRMS and their relationship with dietary polyphenols in adolescents, *Antioxidants* 11 (2022) 1167, <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11061167>.
- R. Mateos, L. Goya, L. Bravo, Metabolism of the olive oil phenols hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, and hydroxytyrosyl acetate by human hepatoma HepG2 cells, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 53 (2005) 9897–9905, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf051721q>.
- Cecilia Bender, Sarah strassmann and christian golz oral bioavailability and metabolism of hydroxytyrosol from food supplements cecilia, *Food Law Policy Ethics* (2020) 272–274, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781843142249-33>.
- M. Suárez, R.M. Valls, M.P. Romero, A. MacIà, S. Fernández, M. Giralt, R. Solà, M. J. Motilva, Bioavailability of phenols from a phenol-enriched olive oil, *Br. J. Nutr.* 106 (2011) 1691–1701, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007114511002200>.
- C. Salis, L. Papageorgiou, E. Papakonstantinou, M. Hagidimitriou, D. Vlachakis, Olive oil polyphenols in neurodegenerative pathologies, *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 1195 (2020) 77–91, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32633-3_12.
- R. Estruch, E. Ros, J. Salas-Salvado, M.-I. Covas, D. Corella, F. Arós, E. Gómez-Gracia, V. Ruiz-Gutiérrez, M. Fiol, J. Lapetra, et al., Primary prevention of cardiovascular disease with a mediterranean diet supplemented with extra-virgin olive oil or nuts, *N. Engl. J. Med.* 378 (2018) e34, <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa1800389>.
- T. Nikou, V. Liaki, P. Stathopoulos, A.D. Sklirou, E.N. Tsakiri, T. Jakschitz, G. Bonn, I.P. Trougagos, M. Halabalaki, L.A. Skaltsounis, Comparison survey of EVOO polyphenols and exploration of healthy aging-promoting properties of oleocanthal and oleacein, *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 125 (2019) 403–412, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfct.2019.01.016>.
- T. Nikou, M.E. Sakavitsi, E. Kalampokis, M. Halabalaki, Metabolism and Bioavailability of Olive Bioactive Constituents Based on In Vitro, *In Vivo and Human Studies* 14 (2022) 3021072747.
- C. Fytili, T. Nikou, N. Tentolouris, I.K. Tseti, C. Dimosthenopoulos, P.P. Sfikakis, D. Simos, A. Kokkinos, A.L. Skaltsounis, N. Katsilambros, et al., Effect of long-term hydroxytyrosol administration on body weight, fat mass and urine metabolomics: a randomized double-blind prospective human study, *Nutrition* 14 (2022).
- A. Angelis, L. Antoniadou, P. Stathopoulos, M. Halabalaki, L.A. Skaltsounis, Oleocanthal and oleaceic acids: new compounds from extra virgin olive oil (EVOO), *Phytochem. Lett.* 26 (2018) 190–194, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2018.06.020>.
- S. Bouatra, F. Aziat, R. Mandal, A.C. Guo, M.R. Wilson, C. Knox, T.C. Bjorn Dahl, R. Krishnamurthy, F. Saleem, P. Liu, et al., The human urine metabolome, *PLoS One* 8 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0073076>.
- L. Da Silva, M. Godejohann, F.P.J. Martin, S. Collino, A. Bürkle, M. Moreno-Villanueva, J. Bernhardt, O. Toussaint, B. Grubeck-Loebenstein, E.S. Gonos, et al., High-resolution quantitative metabolome analysis of urine by automated flow injection NMR, *Anal. Chem.* 85 (2013) 5801–5809, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac4004776>.
- J. Rodríguez-Morató, Ó.J. Pozo, J. Marcos, Targeting human urinary metabolome by LC-MS/MS: a review, *Bioanalysis* 10 (2018) 489–516, <https://doi.org/10.4155/bio-2017-0285>.
- A.H. Emwas, R. Roy, R.T. McKay, D. Ryan, L. Brennan, L. Tenori, C. Luchinat, X. Gao, A.C. Zeri, G.A.N. Gowda, et al., Recommendations and standardization of biomarker quantification using NMR-based metabolomics with particular focus on urinary analysis, *J. Proteome Res.* 15 (2016) 360–373, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.5b00885>.
- E.J. Saude, B.D. Sykes, Urine stability for metabolomic studies: effects of preparation and storage, *Metabolomics* 3 (2007) 19–27, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11306-006-0042-2>.
- L. Whiley, E. Chekmeneva, D.J. Berry, B. Jiménez, A.H.Y. Yuen, A. Salam, H. Hussain, M. Witt, Z. Takats, J. Nicholson, et al., Systematic isolation and structure elucidation of urinary metabolites optimized for the analytical-scale molecular profiling laboratory, *Anal. Chem.* 91 (2019) 8873–8882, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.9b00241>.
- M.A. Fernández-Peralbo, M.D. Luque de Castro, Preparation of urine samples prior to targeted or untargeted metabolomics mass-spectrometry analysis, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 41 (2012) 75–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2012.08.011>.
- E.J. Want, I.D. Wilson, H. Gika, G. Theodoridis, R.S. Plumb, J. Shokcor, E. Holmes, J.K. Nicholson, Global metabolic profiling procedures for urine using UPLC-MS, *Nat. Protoc.* 5 (2010) 1005–1018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2010.50>.
- N. Zhang, K. Rogers, K. Gajda, J.R. Kagel, D.T. Rossi, Integrated sample collection and handling for drug discovery bioanalysis, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 23 (2000) 551–560, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085\(00\)00336-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085(00)00336-8).
- P.L. Kole, G. Venkatesh, J. Kotecha, R. Sheshala, Recent advances in sample preparation techniques for effective bioanalytical methods, *Biomed. Chromatogr.* 25 (2011) 199–217, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bmc.1560>.
- A.D. Southam, L.D. Haglington, L. Najdekr, A. Jankevics, R.J.M. Weber, W. B. Dunn, Assessment of human plasma and urine sample preparation for reproducible and high-throughput UHPLC-MS clinical metabolic phenotyping, *Analyst* 145 (2020) 6511–6523, <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0an01319f>.
- J.C. Domínguez-Romero, J.F. García-Reyes, A. Molina-Díaz, Comparative evaluation of seven different sample treatment approaches for large-scale multiclass sport drug testing in urine by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1361 (2014) 34–42, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.07.090>.
- E. Tuentner, M.E. Sakavitsi, A. Rivera-Mondragón, N. Hermans, K. Foubert, M. Halabalaki, L. Pieters, Ruby chocolate: a study of its phytochemical composition and quantitative comparison with dark, milk and white chocolate, *Food Chem.* 343 (2021) 128446, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.128446>.
- J.L. Wolfender, J.M. Nuzillard, J.J.J. Van Der Hooft, J.H. Renault, S. Bertrand, Accelerating metabolite identification in natural product research: toward an ideal combination of liquid chromatography-high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry and NMR profiling, in silico databases, and chemometrics, *Anal. Chem.* 91 (2019) 704–742, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.8b05112>.
- J.M. Posma, I. Garcia-Perez, J.C. Heaton, P. Burdisso, J.C. Mathers, J. Draper, M. Lewis, J.C. Lindon, G. Frost, E. Holmes, et al., Integrated analytical and statistical two-dimensional spectroscopy strategy for metabolite identification: application to dietary biomarkers, *Anal. Chem.* 89 (2017) 3300–3309, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.6b03324>.
- V.L. Stevens, E. Hoover, Y. Wang, K.A. Zanetti, Pre-analytical factors that affect metabolite stability in human urine, plasma, and serum: a review, *Metabolites* 9 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo9080156>.
- P. Bernini, I. Bertini, C. Luchinat, P. Nincheri, S. Staderini, P. Turano, Standard operating procedures for pre-analytical handling of blood and urine for metabolomic studies and biobanks, *J. Biomol. NMR* 49 (2011) 231–243, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10858-011-9489-1>.
- W. Ammerlaan, J.P. Trezzi, C. Mathay, K. Hiller, F. Betsou, Method validation for preparing urine samples for downstream proteomic and metabolomic applications,

- Biopreserv. Biobanking 12 (2014) 351–357, <https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2014.0013>.
- [34] K. Budde, Ö.N. Gök, M. Pietzner, C. Meisinger, M. Leitzmann, M. Nauck, A. Köttgen, N. Friedrich, Quality assurance in the pre-analytical phase of human urine samples by ¹H NMR spectroscopy, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.* 589 (2016) 10–17, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abb.2015.07.016>.
- [35] H.G. Gika, G.A. Theodoridis, J.E. Wingate, I.D. Wilson, Within-day reproducibility of an HPLC-MS-based method for metabolomic analysis: application to human urine, *J. Proteome Res.* 6 (2007) 3291–3303, <https://doi.org/10.1021/pr070183p>.
- [36] C. Xiao, F. Hao, X. Qin, Y. Wang, H. Tang, An optimized buffer system for NMR-based urinary metabolomics with effective pH control, chemical shift consistency and dilution minimization, *Analyst* 134 (2009) 916–925, <https://doi.org/10.1039/b818802e>.
- [37] J. Tchoumchoua, D. Njamen, J.C. Mbanya, A.L. Skaltsounis, M. Halabalaki, Structure-oriented UHPLC-LTQ Orbitrap-based approach as a dereplication strategy for the identification of isoflavonoids from *Amphimas pterocarpoides* crude extract, *J. Mass Spectrom.* 48 (2013) 561–575, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jms.3167>.
- [38] R.J. Raterink, P.W. Lindenburg, R.J. Vreeken, R. Ramautar, T. Hankemeier, Recent developments in sample-pretreatment techniques for mass spectrometry-based metabolomics, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 61 (2014) 157–167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2014.06.003>.
- [39] A. Andrade-Eiroa, M. Canle, V. Leroy-Cancellieri, V. Cerdà, Solid-phase extraction of organic compounds: a critical review. part ii, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* 80 (2016) 655–667, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2015.08.014>.
- [40] R. Quirantes-Piné, V. Verardo, D. Arráez-Román, S. Fernández-Arroyo, V. Micol, M. F. Caboni, A. Segura-Carretero, A. Fernández-Gutiérrez, Evaluation of different extraction approaches for the determination of phenolic compounds and their metabolites in plasma by nanoLC-ESI-TOF-MS, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 404 (2012) 3081–3090, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-012-6402-z>.
- [41] Wenkui Li, Jian Wenying, Y. Fu, *Sample Preparation in LC-MS Bioanalysis*, 2014. ISBN 9781118054697.
- [42] D. Vuckovic, *Sample Preparation in Global Metabolomics of Biological Fluids and Tissues*, second ed., Elsevier Inc., 2019. ISBN 9780128186077.
- [43] A. Agalias, P. Magiatis, A.L. Skaltsounis, E. Mikros, A. Tzarbopoulos, E. Gikas, I. Spanos, T. Manios, A new process for the management of olive oil mill waste water and recovery of natural antioxidants, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 55 (2007) 2671–2676, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf063091d>.
- [44] Q.W. Zhang, L.G. Lin, W.C. Ye, Techniques for extraction and isolation of natural products: a comprehensive review, *Chinese Med. (United Kingdom)* 13 (2018) 1–26, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13020-018-0177-x>.
- [45] X. Cheng, H. Li, P. Wu, L. Xu, J. Xue, X. Wei, Two new bisabolane-type sesquiterpenoids from the cooking liquid of *Curcuma longa* rhizomes, *Phytochem. Lett.* 29 (2019) 169–172, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytol.2018.12.004>.
- [46] A.K. Aissat, N. Chaher-Bazizi, T. Richard, D. Kilani-Atmani, E. Pedrot, E. Renouf, D. Atmani, J. Valls Fonayet, Analysis of individual anthocyanins, flavanols, flavonols and other polyphenols in *Pistacia lentiscus* L. fruits during ripening, *J. Food Compos. Anal.* 106 (2022) 104286, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2021.104286>.
- [47] G. Belen, L. Ringele, S. Beteinakis, A. Papachristodoulou, E. Axiotis, NMR metabolite profiling in the quality & authentication assessment of Greek honey – exploitation of STOCSY for markers' identification, *Foods* (2022) 1–18, doi.org/10.3390/foods11182853.